

POLITICAL SCIENCES

AZERBAIJAN-ARMENIA BORDER ISSUE AND EUROPE

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Abstract

The de jure Azerbaijani-Armenian border corresponds to the border between the former Azerbaijani SSR and the Armenian SSR. The border between the countries consists of two main parts: In the west between Armenia and the Nakhchivan exclave of Azerbaijan, a longer section between Armenia and "mainland" Azerbaijan in the east. In addition, there are a number of enclaves on both sides of the de jure border, but in fact they are now under the control of the respective states. In fact, the situation on the Azerbaijani-Armenian border is more complicated - the western part of the border, Nakhchivan, is not disputed (except for the Karki enclave), but Azerbaijan does not control part of the eastern border. After the victory of Azerbaijan in the Second Karabakh War, the process of returning the occupied territories to the state to which they belonged began. Along with this victory, it also brought territorial and border issues. The article examines the process of restoring peace between the two countries, the mutual recognition and confirmation of borders, as well as the role of Europe in this process.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Armenia, border, dispute, Europe.

Brief information about borders. The territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, located in the east of the South Caucasus, is 86.6 thousand km². The republic borders on land with 5 countries - the Republic of Turkey, the Russian Federation, the Islamic Republic of Iran, the republics of Armenia and Georgia. The Caspian Sea is located in the east of the country and has a water border with Turkmenistan and Kazakhstan. Azerbaijan borders Armenia in the west and southwest. The length of the border with this country is 1007 km. The Karabakh conflict, which began in the early 1990s, resulted in the territorial losses of Azerbaijan. After the escalation of the Karabakh conflict, the official eastern part of the border was formed by the "Line of Contact", which stretched almost halfway and the southern sector of the border inside Azerbaijan, covering not only the mountainous region of Karabakh but also a significant part of Azerbaijan. [10] Armenia occupied twenty percent of Azerbaijan's territories. As a result of the Armenian occupation, the so-called Nagorno-Karabakh Republic was formed in the occupied territory, Azerbaijan lost control of most of its state border with both Armenia and Iran.

Postwar and borders. The issue of demarcation of the border between Azerbaijan and Armenia arose immediately after Armenia was defeated in the Second Karabakh war in 2020 and Azerbaijan regained control over the occupied territories. After the end of the 44-day Patriotic War with the glorious Victory of Azerbaijan, the beginning of new geopolitical processes in the South Caucasus, the foundation of a new era in the history of the region was laid. Until the war of 2020, there was no physical border between Armenia and the regions of Azerbaijan occupied by Armenia, and some Armenian villages were expanding towards the territory of Azerbaijan. In addition, there are other issues related to the border, as Armenia has controlled several villages of Azerbaijan's Gazakh district since the 1990s, including three Azerbaijani enclaves, as well as the Kerki exclave village of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

The conflict has already ended, and in the post-war period, the parties are trying to find solutions to important issues such as the demarcation of the state border, in addition to opening transport links. This process is of great importance for the future security and stability of the region. Now all the processes in the region are taking place under the clear leadership of Azerbaijan. With the signing of a peace agreement between Azerbaijan and Armenia after the second Karabakh war, a security environment, favorable conditions for lasting stability and peace can be created in the region. [4]

Azerbaijan only restores internationally recognized borders. The Azerbaijani side continues the work of strengthening the border protection system implemented within the framework of the liberated territorial integrity. This process is carried out on the basis of the maps of each of the parties that determine the border line between Armenia and Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan is fully committed to peace, security and regional cooperation based on respect for sovereignty, territorial integrity and the inviolability of internationally recognized borders.

Along with the November 10 agreement signed after the victory of the Azerbaijani army in Karabakh, the process of border demarcation between the two countries has started within the framework of the normalization process. Delimitation and demarcation of the borders between the two countries is the main condition for the realization of many projects, including the establishment of a new cooperation format of the regional states and the creation of the Zangezur corridor. Demarcation of borders is a very necessary process, the number one issue of mutual cooperation and insurance against future conflicts that may occur between the parties in the existing border areas.

According to the terms of the November 10 agreement, the remnants of the Armenian army must leave the lands of Azerbaijan, which are currently under the control of Russian peacekeepers. In the current geopolitical conditions, the Armenian decision-makers, from the government to the opposition, should

understand the necessity of opening the Zangezur corridor.[7] Armenia should shape its policy and prepare for a peace agreement and cooperation with Turkey and Azerbaijan.

Azerbaijan and Armenia are trying to restore their relations after the war. Although a ceasefire has been reached, many outstanding issues remain to be resolved in order to move towards a negotiated, comprehensive and sustainable settlement. Despite the mutual statements of both sides, the tension on the border attracts the attention of the US, the OSCE Chairman-in-Office, the leaders of Russia and France. Despite the calls of two of the three co-chairs of the OSCE Minsk Group - the United States and France, Armenia has not withdrawn its troops from the internationally recognized territory of Azerbaijan. [3] The EU has expressed its readiness to provide expertise and assistance on border delimitation and demarcation, including support for much-needed confidence-building measures, to move towards sustainable peace and prosperity for the South Caucasus. [2]

The role of Europe. After Russia's intervention in Ukraine, this process has accelerated somewhat. International organizations and individual interested countries express their support for the signing of the peace treaty between Azerbaijan and Armenia and the demarcation of borders. The leaders of Azerbaijan and Armenia have already met several times in Russia and Europe. Contacts between Aliyev and Pashinyan took place either through the mediation of Brussels or Russia. The Armenian side insists on continuing the Russia-Azerbaijan-Armenia format in the negotiation process. Because Russia is a strategic ally of Armenia. Another format, that is, the Azerbaijan-Armenia-EU format, does not meet its interests, so it tries to slow down this process as much as it can. Russia is trying to maintain its dominance in the South Caucasus, peace between Azerbaijan and Armenia does not serve Putin's goals.

The main issues reflected in the statement signed during the tripartite meeting in Sochi on November 26, 2021 were the removal of the blockade of transport links and the establishment of a bilateral commission on the determination of the state border between Azerbaijan and Armenia. [9] The resolution of the issues mentioned in the statement, especially the delimitation and demarcation of the state border, is considered an important preparatory stage for the signing of the peace agreement. While Azerbaijan is fully determined to fulfill its obligations, Armenia is deliberately delaying the resolution of these issues. Although Armenian officials often make various statements of reconciliation nature, when it comes to concrete joint work, they refrain from it under various pretexts. Even after the bitter defeat in the war, the Armenian diaspora in the USA and France, as well as some insidious forces in Armenia, continue to poison the point of view of their compatriots and do not want to give up revanchist feelings.

The reason why the border clarifications have not been realized so far is the non-constructive position of the official Yerevan, its inability to digest the real situation in the region, living with utopian ideas such as

the so-called NKR getting the status with the help of international institutions, mainly the Minsk Group of the OSCE. [8]

On March 30, a meeting of high-level representatives of Armenia and Azerbaijan was held in Brussels with the mediation of the EU. Here, they agreed on the necessity of continuing this relationship in order to ensure the adequate continuation of the agreements reached at the level of leaders. [1] On April 6, a working lunch meeting was held between Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev, Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan and European Union Council President Charles Michel in Brussels. After the meeting, the President of the Council of the European Union Charles Michel said that stability, security and development in the South Caucasus are very important for the European Union. [6] It raises the hope that the meetings of both sides with the mediation of the President of the Council of the European Union will have successful results. The agenda of the Brussels peace meeting is part of the proposals put forward by President Ilham Aliyev for the post-conflict period. President C.Michel called keeping forces at an appropriate distance an important element in preventing incidents and reducing tensions. He once again stressed that the EU is ready to provide advice and support in this matter. For delimitation and demarcation of bilateral borders, in accordance with the Sochi Declaration of November 26, 2021, it was agreed to establish a Joint Border Commission by the end of April. However, due to the delays of the Armenian side, the organization of the commission was postponed until May.

On May 23, the tripartite meeting was held in Brussels with EU Council Chairman Charles Michel, President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and Prime Minister of Armenia Nikol Pashinyan. According to the information of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Azerbaijan, at the meeting, the parties confirmed their readiness to work within the framework of the Commission on delimitation and other issues. [11] President Michel noted that both President Aliyev and Prime Minister Pashinyan expressed their desire to move quickly towards a peace agreement between their countries. For this purpose, the foreign ministers are asked to prepare a future peace agreement that will resolve all the necessary issues. It was agreed to be assigned to work on it. The leaders discussed the restoration of communication infrastructure between Armenia and Azerbaijan, especially in the South Caucasus. President Michel welcomed the steps taken towards the restoration of railway lines, and at the same time encouraged Armenia and Azerbaijan to find effective solutions for the restoration of road connections. The leaders agreed to follow up on the results of their meeting and to continue relations.

The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, announced the specific position of Azerbaijan that when defining borders, history should be taken into account, and maps from the period after the Sovietization of the South Caucasus should be used. He noted: *"We should not dwell on only one map, because there are many maps - there is a map of 1918,*

when Irevan was a part of Azerbaijan. There is a map of November 1920 that Zangezur was a part of Azerbaijan at that time. In addition, at that time, Azerbaijanis lived in the territories along the Iran-Armenia border, and those lands had nothing to do with the Armenian people. In November 1920, the Soviet authorities decided to give Zangezur to Armenia. However, when this territory was given to Armenia, it did not have today's area - 42 kilometers, the area was narrower. However, the Armenians expanded the area to 42 kilometers, and today the border with Iran passes through it. Thus, our position is that we will use all the maps - from 1918 and even earlier to maps up to the collapse of the Soviet Union. Of course, this will be part of the negotiations of our joint working groups.” [5] President Aliyev expressed his hope that the meeting in the tripartite format will be result-oriented as a continuation of the Brussels peace agenda. The President Michel noted the importance of the dialogue between Armenia and Azerbaijan. He highly appreciated the role played by Azerbaijan in Europe's energy security.

One day after the tripartite meeting, President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and Prime Minister of Armenia Nikol Pashinyan signed an order on the establishment of border delimitation commissions. Azerbaijani and Armenian Deputy Prime Ministers Shahin Mustafayev and Mher Grigoryan met at the Armenian-Azerbaijani border. At the first meeting, the organizational and procedural issues of the commission's joint activity were discussed. [11] The parties agreed to hold meetings in different places in addition to the meetings at the interstate border. However, recent border clashes are delaying the peace process.

In **conclusion**, starting the process of border delimitation and demarcation in good faith is the only way to resolve all disputes that may arise, which is a key to ensuring peace and security.

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